

Functional Features of Somatic Phraseological Units in the Russian Language

Bakieva Mokhlaroy Nematjon kizi

Master's student, Fergana State University

Mamadzhanova G. M. (PhD)

Associate Professor

Article information:

Manuscript received: 28 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 27 Nov 2024; **Published:** 3 Dec 2024

Abstract: This article explores the functioning of somatic phraseological units in the Russian language. The study covers the concept of somatic phraseological units (SPUs), their components, and lexical groups, as well as their frequency and connotations. Examples of the most frequently used SPUs and their impact on the perception and expression of various aspects of human life are provided. Additionally, the article discusses problems and prospects for further research in this field.

Keywords: somatic phraseological units, Russian language, semantics, structure, connotation, frequency, phraseology, lexicon, linguistic studies.

A somatic phraseological unit (SFE) is a phraseological unit that includes a component denoting a part of the human body, such as the nose, head, or hand, or elements of the cardiovascular or nervous systems, such as liver, blood, or brain. These are nouns that denote body parts. These phrases arise spontaneously in language and are based on a person's experience of themselves and their bodies.

Somatic phraseological units have been partially studied by scholars such as A.M. Chepasova, V.A. Lebedinskaya, and N.F. Alefirenko. Researchers such as Yu.A. Dolgoplov and F.F. Vakk have also considered SFE data in their work. Most scholars agree that SFE are among the oldest categories of vocabulary.

Somatic vocabulary can be divided into six groups:

1. Sonomic vocabulary (parts and areas of the human body)
2. Angionymic vocabulary (circulatory system)
3. Osteonymic vocabulary (bones of the body)
4. Vocabulary for the designation of diseases
5. Splanchnonymic vocabulary (internal organs)
6. Sensonymic vocabulary (sensory organs)

The analysis of the units was carried out by understanding the definitions of phraseological units from the Phraseological Dictionary of Russian edited by A. I. Molotkov. We have categorized the somaticisms according to their frequency.

Head - 39: hitting like a butt on the head, knocking the barrel out of the head, hammering it into the head, knocking it off from a sick head to a healthy one, not taking down the head, bringing the guilty head, giving the head off, having a head on your shoulders, like snow on your head, even when your head is against the wall, sticking your head in a noose, even the stake on the head is scratchy, it does not fit in your head, without a king in your head.

Eyes - 47: getting in front of my eyes, glaring at me, my eyes not seeing, spinning in front of me, not believing what my eyes see, an eyesore, wherever my eyes look, dust blowing in my eyes, not just in one eye, I didn't have time to blink, light fading in my eyes, creating eyes, growing in front of my eyes, looking with other eyes, not being able to believe my eyes, hitting in the eyes.

Hand - 74: Jack of all trades, let your hands do what they want, take control of your hands, gather yourself, let go of what's in your hands, something burns in your palms, your hands will not shake, your own hands, spread your fingers, lick your palms, be gentle with your hands, second-hand, hit your hands as if they were empty, from hand to hand, right hand.

Heart - 29: tear out of your heart, let your heart do what it wants, hold onto your heart, with a kind heart, find your way to the center of someone's heart, enter their heart, big heart, deeply in your heart, your heart is not where it should be, give your hand and your heart, tear your heart, reluctantly, tear from your heart.

Teeth - 26: sharpen your teeth, one tooth at a time, put your teeth away, look at your teeth, bite your tooth, eat your tooth, break a tooth, show your smile, talk with your teeth, not on your tooth, not between your teeth, keep quiet.

Thus, the analysis revealed that phraseology is dominated by words referring to the sense organs through which people perceive reality and learn about the world. The most common somatic components in Russian are head, hand, eye, heart, and teeth, accounting for almost 50% of all somatic phraseological units in this study. Additionally, there are isolated examples of shoulder blade and heel.

Furthermore, it is worth noting the connotative meanings of the most common somatic phraseological expressions. For instance, the head is associated with thinking, as a "bad head" does not allow one to rest their feet. Values and abilities are expressed through phrases like "golden head," while the inner character and qualities are conveyed through expressions such as "wind in one's head."

Language is responsible for communication, and it often has a negative connotation. It can convey the meaning of excessive talkativeness, such as scratching one's tongue or talking with one's mouth. There are also examples with the meanings of "slacker" or "lazy," as well as "empty-headed." A negative assessment of language can also be given when it harms others, such as with expressions like "evil tongue" or "cow licked with tongue."

The eyes are symbols of receiving information, and most examples with this somatism indicate positive or negative qualities within a person, as well as their character. Eyes are often described as a mirror of the soul and can reflect the emotional state of a person. Arm is a word that can be used in different ways, such as referring to mastery of hands or activity, but it can also have negative semantics such as hiding other people's wrongdoings.

The mouth, like the tongue, plays an important role in communication and conveying information. Therefore, the word "mouth" has similar meanings in the English language. There are many phrases that describe talking or being talkative, such as "the mouth does not shut up" or "like water in the mouth."

The analysis showed that the Russian language has a rich vocabulary of words that refer to the sense organs that help us perceive the world around us. These words include "head," "eyes," "hand," "heart," and "teeth." These body parts account for 49.7% of all somatic

phraseological units in the study. There are also some examples with less common body parts, such as "nail," "shoulder blade," "heel," and "liver."

Somatic expressions (SFE) are among the most commonly used words in the creation of phraseological units in the Russian language. A high proportion of the use of somatic expressions is a characteristic feature of the phraseology system in Russian. The components "head", "hand", "heart", and "teeth" correspond directly to the sensory and logical stages of perception. These areas belong to the most frequent zones of the lexicon.

Somatic expressions belong to the oldest category of vocabulary used in the formation of phraseological expressions. They are characterized by a high frequency of usage and stability. The abundance of somatic expressions can be explained by the clear functions of body parts. According to our research, more than 50 somatic expressions are involved in the creation of phraseological expressions in Russian.

The main functions of various body parts, such as the head, eyes, hands, heart, and teeth, determine the content of the main thematic groups of phraseological units with somatic components. These phrases reflect different types of human activities (mental and physical), as well as a person's mental and physical state, and, of course, they generally reflect the relationships between people (their communicative and pragmatic qualities).

A promising direction for future research in this area would be to study the grammatical features of phraseological units containing somatic components and their use in Russian and other languages.

It is only through the study of these phraseological units that we can approach the solution to many important problems in modern linguistics, such as semantics, pragmatics, and the interaction between the properties of the phrase and its use in language.

References

1. Alefirenko N.F. Theoretical foundations of the doctrine of the "inner form" of phraseological units. // Semantics of language units. Reports of the V International Conference. Volume 1. MGOPI. M., 1996.
2. Wack F.O. On somatic phraseology in the modern Estonian literary language: Abstract of the dissertation of the Candidate of Philology. Tallinn, 1964.; Dolgoplov Yu.A. Comparative analysis of somatic phraseology (based on the material of Russian, English and German. languages): Dis. Candidate of Philology. sciences. Kazan, 1973.
3. Sknar V.F. Verbal somatic phraseological units of the modern English language: Abstract. Dissertation of the Candidate of Philology. Kiev, 1978. — 25 p.
4. Phraseological dictionary of the Russian language [Text]: Over 4000 dictionary entries / Comp. L. A. Voynova, V. P. Zhukov, A. I. Molotkov, A. I. Fedorov; Edited by A. I. Molotkov. - 2nd ed., revised. - Moscow: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1968. - 543 p.
5. Chepasova A.M. The World of Russian phraseology. Chelyabinsk: ChSPU, 1998. 216 p.; Lebedinskaya V.A. Semantics of procedural phraseological units / V.A. Lebedinskaya, N.B. Usacheva. Kurgan: Publishing House of the Kurgan State University, 1999. -185 p.